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D7.1 – Consumer Validation Report v1

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This deliverable will present the methodology for consumer validation of ACCEPT solutions, as well as document the barriers and drivers that influence the types of digital services stakeholders find most valuable. It will also identify engagement channels for co-creation with consumers in order to understand user preferences, needs and limitations related to ACCEPT services. This first report will present the overall methodology for consumer validation, while the updates in M33 and M42 will provide more detailed assessment of the outcomes of consumer validation activities.

Successful exploitation of solutions and business models is reliant on gathering stakeholder feedback on products and services from the early development stage through to the project's conclusion. ACCEPT services validation methodology encompasses three phases: pre-analysis, pre-validation, and user validation as a part of ACCEPT living labs concept. The pre-analysis has been mainly conducted through background studies (D3.2 and D3.3), consumer engagement and design validation activities in WP3, and a concept testing survey (D2.1) together with other activities in WP2. Pre-validation will be conducted at ACCEPT testbeds before full deployment of solutions to selected consumers in the pilot sites, and co-creation activities to assess people's lived experiences with the solutions.

The validation and co-creation roadmap include a range of activities: First step will be design of user personas to reflect different real-world user types and are used to guide the design decisions of tool and service developers. User personas will be validated in workshops in each of the pilot sites.

The second step involves both technical testing ACCEPT solutions at pre-validation test beds and user testing of ACCEPT user interfaces, including citizen apps and community tool's user interfaces. Early testing and continuous collection of user feedback are key cornerstones for successful design and subsequent adaptation of the solutions.

Following pre-validation, the ACCEPT solutions will be fully deployed at pilot sites and end users will be engaged in co-creation activities to assess their views, needs and preferences related to ACCEPT solutions and services. The aim is to bring hassle-free benefits to consumers with minimal level of intrusion and maintaining living comfort. ACCEPT Living Lab concept will be a main enabler of communication and information between the consumers, pilot sites, and the technical development teams through hybrid collaboration approach presented in D3.1.

ACCEPT user validation strategy includes validation of business models and related feedback towards the end of the project.

Tools and methods for end-user engagement include user-centred methods including interviews, focus groups, workshops, user experience questionnaires and system usability scale assessments. Tools utilized will be defined for each co-creation round, depending on the type of the session and solutions or services to be tested. While the aim is to hold as many presentational sessions with the end-users as possible, a range of digital tools for engagement can be utilized should, for example, the COVID19 situation prohibit organization of presentational workshops.

ABBREVIATIONS

AIC	Arena Innovation Community
BC	Business Case
BRP	Balance responsible parties
DSO	Distribution system operator
ESCO	Energy service company
EV	Electric Vehicle
KPI	Key Performance Indicators
LL	Living Lab
SUS	System Usability Scale
TSO	Transmission system operator
UC	Use Case
UEQ	User experience questionnaire
UX	User experience

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1. Introduction

1.1. Scope and objectives of task

This deliverable will present the methodology for consumer validation of ACCEPT solutions, as well as document some of the barriers and drivers that influence the types of digital services stakeholders find most valuable. It will also identify engagement channels for co-creation with end-users in order to understand user preferences, needs and limitations related to ACCEPT services. The first report will present the overall methodology for consumer validation, while the updates in M33 and M42 will provide more detailed assessment of the outcome of consumer validation activities.

1.2. Structure of deliverable

The deliverable will follow the structure defined below:

- Chapter 2 sets the theoretical and methodological framework for user validation in ACCEPT and describes the process.
- Chapter 3 describes the contextualization of user-types process through presenting the methodology for persona creation.
- Chapter 4 discusses ACCEPT use cases and services to be tested and presents results from the preliminary analysis and concept testing.
- Chapter 5 discussed ACCEPT tools to be tested and presents the plan for co-creation throughout the project.
- Chapter 6 discusses stakeholders to be engaged and engagement channels for co-creation.
- Chapter 7 presents the ACCEPT user validation roadmap and timeline.

1.3. Interdependencies with other tasks and deliverables

The ACCEPT user validation process is closely linked to a range of other project activities and deliverables presenting interdependencies between technical development, user engagement, pilot site deployment and Living Lab activities, as well as wider communication activities.

The recruitment and preliminary selection of candidate participants who will also contribute to the user validation activities were carried out under the framework of the ex-ante pilot surveys conducted in task T6.1 of WP6. The LL activities and citizen engagement also contributed to the citizen recruitment at pilot sites. The activities presented here are also linked to other deliverables connected with the LL, community mapping, and co-creation activities reported in D3.2, D3.7 and D3.5. The activities and outreach links to the LL objectives in WP3 for task T3.1, which describe the pilot specific activities. D3.3 and D3.4 provided theoretical background for energy communities and governance and D2.1 contributed to the understanding of user preferences and barriers related to ACCEPT services.

The co-creation process is further related to ACCEPT tools and services development: WP4 will design building level tools and solutions, and WP5 community level solutions as well as citizen apps to be tested. WP6 will further contribute through solution integration, pre-validation and rollout, before full consumer validation under T7.1. Co-creation activities will be conducted already during pre-validation, and they will be further continued after the full deployment of the tools.

2. ACCEPT services validation methodology

Successful exploitation of solutions and business models is reliant on gathering stakeholder feedback on products and services from the development stage through to the project’s conclusion. ACCEPT services validation methodology is set to guarantee that Accept solutions will meet user preferences and requirements, they will be easy to use, and energy communities will find the solutions useful both for individuals as well as for the community as a whole.

The methodology encompasses three phases: pre-analysis, pre-validation, and user validation as a part of ACCEPT living labs concept.

The first phase involves, amongst others, analysing theoretical background and conducting concept testing and use case validation under WP2 and WP3, especially through D2.1, as well as forthcoming user persona creation under WP3 to define the user profiles, together with divers and barriers to guide the design of ACCEPT consumer tools.

The second phase consists of testing and validating ACCEPT solutions in controlled environments, so-called “test-beds” where the technical tools will be tested in controlled real life situations. Parallel to this process, ACCEPT user interfaces will be tested with consumers and other end users.

The third phase consist of testing ACCEPT tools and services in real-life situations through living lab framework in ACCEPT pilot sites as a part of demonstration and validation activities in WP7. The lived experiences of consumers will be explored and tested through iterative process of co-creation sessions or focus groups and possibly other means of data collection to fine tune the solutions and services to allow energy flexibility without compromising comfort or customer’s ability to control their lived environment. The achievement of project KPIs related to user acceptance and user satisfaction will also be monitored.

Hybrid collaboration approach (D3.1) is a central piece of validation activities; while the approach is focused on engagement within the project in a wider scale than just engagement for user validation, user validation forms a central part of citizen engagement activities. This approach consists of two major components: (1) examining the top-down perspective from the project and technical coordinators and (2), gathering information from the bottom-up perspective from work package (WP), task and pilot site leaders. Combining these perspectives allows for the project goals and technical development to be aligned with ground-level needs and preferences, which is essential for guaranteeing information flows between user’s lived experience and technical development as well as wider project goals for exploitation and business development.

Figure 1: ACCEPT tools and services validation methodology

Table 1: ACCEPT KPIs relevant for user validation

Category	KPI	Metric	Target
Co-creation / feedback loops / UX	Co-creation participation	Stakeholders participating in co-creation process	1000
Co-creation / feedback loops / UX	Participation to validation activities	Stakeholders participating in user validation sessions	770
Customer Satisfaction	Citizen satisfaction	Citizen satisfaction from the ACCEPT solution demonstration	Above 75%
Acceptance	Acceptance	Conscious acceptance of the ACCEPT solution	Above 90%

The table above presents ACCEPT KPIs relevant for user validation. First two metrics are related to the number of stakeholders targeted to be reached for co-creation and validation activities, which will be described in this deliverable. Customer satisfaction and acceptance will be assessed as a part of co-creation activities after full deployment of ACCEPT solutions. From the co-creation and user validation perspective, including end-user needs and preferences to design already at an early phase greatly enhances the opportunities to meet the performance targets.

3. Enhancing user experience through contextualisation

ACCEPT seeks to empower consumers to actively change their consumption patterns over time without diminishing their ability to control their lived environment and lifestyle options. Understanding the user values, potential points of resistance, requirements and concerns will help to design services that meet the needs of different user groups and segments of consumers. Effective solutions require contextualization of the solutions to match user needs that will be defined as a part of the process. For example, some people might respond better to messaging related to collective advantage, while others are motivated by individual benefits, and household with children or low energy users might have less possibilities for changing daily energy use routines than other households. Some households might prefer action on a short term based on notifications while others would be more motivated by the opportunities of overall reduction and optimization of energy use.

Personas are intended to reflect different real-world user types and are used to guide the design decisions of tool and service developers by answering the question, “who am I designing for?” (see Figure 2). That is, rather than considering the end user as a homogenous group with identical needs and preferences, design personas allow the tool/service developer to tease out the nuanced difference between users to create fictional characters that allow them to better envision different types of end-users who will ultimately use the product. Personas help developers avoid the common pitfall of designing a product based on themselves (i.e. their own knowledge levels, tech abilities, and interests) rather than the spectrum of actual users. The empathic design approach may result in the development of several different products or services, with each tailored to specific persona types, or one solution that has been intelligently designed to address the needs and preferences of multiple persona groups.

Figure 2: ACCEPT design persona mock-up example

It is important to note that design personas are not the same as market segments. While they do indeed share a similar goal of dividing a larger population into smaller subgroups, design personas aim to create a vivid profile that describes the customer journey of an end-user archetype that captures their emotions, values, attitudes, and skills, while a segment will typically be limited to more quantitative descriptors related to simple demographics and market size. While both can be useful in different applications, for the development of the ACCEPT technical solutions, the design persona approach will provide a richer customer-centric framework that can guide tool development.

The ACCEPT project will work to develop several design personas to guide the development of the solutions being developed and applied in each of the pilot sites. The creation of these persona groups will follow a two-step process. First, theoretical personas will be developed based on an extensive literature review. Next, a persona validation workshop/focus group will be held in each pilot community during which community citizens (i.e. end-users) will be interviewed to collect inputs about their skills, behaviours, and perceptions that will help to refine the theoretical

personas into actionable personas that can be built out and applied for the ACCEPT tool design. See the design methodology in Figure 3.

Figure 3: ACCEPT design persona methodology

One should be mindful that the creation of design personas is often more of an art than a science and requires a certain degree of creative interpretation to capture the essence of particular user type. Nevertheless, the exercise of creating and using these profiles can offer huge benefits in for ensuring a user-centric design.

Some of the best practices identified for user-centric design include engaging a wide range of stakeholder perspectives, early engagement, as well as regular feedback to the users on the results and how the information collected from them will be used. These principles will be utilized to guarantee the effects of the co-creation process starting from the user-type definition through persona creation and continuing throughout the co-creation process.

The ACCEPT design persona methodology presented in Figure 3 is expected to be conducted according to the timeline provided in Table 2. This process will feed into the general ACCEPT co-creation roadmap presented in the Chapter 8.

Table 2: ACCEPT persona creation timeline

Action	Responsible	Timeline
1. Persona design methodology and timeline	Geco Global / Accept pilot sites	M12
2. Literature review and theoretical characterization	Geco Global	M13-M14
3. Design persona validation workshop methodology	Geco Global / Accept pilot sites	M14-M15
4. Conduct validation workshops at pilot sites, preferably focus group meetings, moderated in local language	Accept pilot sites/ selected moderators / Geco Global	M15-M16
5. Finalise personas	Geco Global	M16-M17
6. Share back information with ACCEPT internal and external stakeholders	Geco Global	M17-M18

4. Accept use cases and services

This chapter presents the ACCEPT services to be tested at the pilot sites through Living Lab approach and summarises key user requirements identified through concept testing in order to pave way to service development, user testing and real-life validation of ACCEPT tools and services.

A set of use cases were identified and strategically designed to test and implement Accept tools and services. The use cases were translated into "Accept services", and utilising language easily understandable to potential end users, the end users' views of the potential services were consulted in a concept testing survey (D2.1). The concept survey sought to assess the end users' views on Accept solutions, including general appeal of the services proposed, barriers related to the implementation of the use cases and willingness to participate in future activities. Altogether 115 end-users, including consumers and prosumers, responded to the survey with 38 respondents from Greece, 35 from Spain, 23 from Switzerland and 19 from the Netherlands. While the full analysis of the survey is available in D2.1, this chapter will highlight some of the main findings which will have relevance from consumer validation perspective.

ACCEPT services to be tested in the pilot sites are presented in the Table 3 below.

Table 3: ACCEPT services to be tested in different pilot sites

Accept consumer services	Pilot site			
	Greece	Spain	Netherlands	Switzerland
1) Energy Consumption App	x	x	x	x
2) Day-ahead Energy Cost App	x	x	x	
3) H&C devices optimization	x	x	x	x
4) Forecasting and optimization of consumer demand flexibility	x	x	x	x
5) Optimal heating schedules				x
6) Elasticity of energy demand profiling-forecasting-aggregation	x	x	x	
7) Participation in a "Demand-Response" Scheme	x	x	x	x
8) Energy generation forecasting				x
9) Monitoring tool for grid stability			x	
Additional services for businesses and energy communities				
10) Calculation and forecasting of electric vehicles charging flexibility				
11) Increase self-generated green electricity consumption				

As can be seen from the Table 3, ACCEPT technical solutions allow a range of services to be developed and implemented both for consumers and service providers alike. In general, the services received positive feedback from the part of the survey respondents. Graph 1 further demonstrates respondents' attitudes towards the concept of energy communities.

Graph 1: Reactions to ACCEPT concept of energy communities

In general, the respondents found Access concept of energy communities appealing, responding either “very appealing” or “somewhat appealing”, which is a promising result for the future. Slight differences exist between the pilot sites: Greece and Spain indicated exceptionally positive attitudes and the Netherlands and Switzerland slightly more neutral ones, even if the overall response in all pilot sites was positive.

Graph 2: Preferred level of involvement

Regarding to the willingness to participate, Spanish and Greek pilot sites demonstrate a high interest in being involved in ACCEPT project, most of the respondents indicating they have an interest to become actively involved. In case of the Netherlands and Switzerland, the respondents showed slightly less interest. Some of the concerns and barriers for joining included lack of information and understanding of the services, perceived administrative burden, lack of time, and possible fear of losing control over home devices.

Related to the services directed to consumers, the respondents found most of the services appealing (responding strongly agree or agree to the statement). The most preferred services were in order of preference: heating and cooling optimization, citizen energy consumption app, energy profiling-aggregation, and forecasting optimization for consumer flexibility.

In relation to willingness to adapt the planned ACCEPT services (see Graph 3) the heating and cooling optimization received most interest, followed by energy consumption app and energy profiling-aggregation. In addition, energy cost forecasting app received high interest from the respondents.

Given that differences exist in the services to be tested at different pilot sites and people’s reactions towards the services at local level varied at different pilot sites, key elements per pilot site will be summarized in the sub-chapters below, followed by recommendations for user-testing and engagement. Full information regarding the preferences and concerns of each pilot site is available in the ACCEPT deliverable 2.1.

Graph 3: Respondent’s willingness to adopt the service

4.1. Aspra Spitia Community, Greece

In Aspra Spitia, preferred ACCEPT services were energy monitoring app, cooling optimization and possibility to influence energy price as a community (Graph 4). 60 % of the respondents wished to participate actively to ACCEPT project.

Graph 4: Willingness to adopt the service, Greece

The major foreseen benefits and factors that the respondents valued in ACCEPT solutions included the shift from fossil fuels to renewable energy and optimization of energy consumption.

The major concerns included the easiness or difficulty of using the solutions, possible lack of time to engage to the project, and a fear of possible impacts on the energy bill, in terms of increased energy bill through transfer to renewable energy sources.

From the solution development perspective, the respondents seem to value the possibility to consume green renewable energy through an energy community and they are interested in participating actively and adapting ACCEPT solutions. The solutions, such as citizen application, should be, however, easy and intuitive to use. Possibility to reduce the energy bill seems to be one of the motivating factors to join.

4.2. Renewable energy cooperative buildings, Spain

In general, the respondents in Spain found the Accept services very appealing. The most appreciated services were an app to follow energy consumption, heating and cooling optimization, as well as possibility to influence energy prices as a community through energy consumption profiling. The respondents were most willing to adapt concrete tools such as energy consumption app, and energy cost prediction app (Graph 5).

Graph 5: Willingness to adopt the service, Spain

Approximately half of the respondents were willing to participate actively in the Accept solution testing process. They indicated willingness to collaborate with the community and become independent from big energy companies.

Major barriers identified included concerns over the number of devices to be installed at homes, possible costs of investment and losing of control over home devices. Potential administrative burden was also addressed as one of the major concerns related to the system.

In terms of future testing and co-creation of services and applications, the expressed high interest towards Accept solutions indicate a positive response towards the tools and services. It will be important, however, ensure that the tools and services will take into account people's concerns over the need to be able to control home devices and the design of the concrete tools in a way that they will be least intrusive possible.

4.3. Eva Lanxmeer Community, the Netherlands

In Eva Lanxmeer Community, respondents expressed some interest in ACCEPT solutions. 35 % found the ACCEPT concept of energy communities appealing, and 29 % were willing to participate actively.

The preferred services were heating and cooling optimization, energy consumption monitoring app and possibility to participate to flexibility markets through community level demand elasticity profiling (Graph 6).

Graph 6: Willingness to adopt the service, Netherlands

The respondents in Eva Lanxmeer community were all prosumers, and as such they can be expected to be already knowledgeable on energy related issues. The main value of ACCEPT solutions expressed by the respondents were increase in sustainability and possibility to utilize electric devices and hybrid cars more efficiently.

The respondents raised concerns such as compatibility of the ACCEPT solutions with systems already in place, ability to maintain interest to energy consumption monitoring, not being able to be flexible in the energy use or monitoring energy prices regularly. Concerns existed about lack of time, data privacy and security, and administrative burden for prosumers contributing to energy flexibility.

From the user testing and service creation perspective, the user interfaces and community solutions designed should have clear benefits to the users beyond energy monitoring, and the solutions should be easy to use and least intrusive possible to increase their attractiveness. Data privacy and security management should be clearly communicated to the participants. Finally, administrative load should be minimized to the extent possible.

4.4. Motta Massagno district, Switzerland

In Motta Massagno district, 35 % of the users found the ACCEPT concept of energy communities appealing. Overall, there seemed to be less interest towards the project, and 13 % of the respondents indicated they would wish to participate to the project actively.

The preferred services were energy consumption monitoring app, and possibility to optimize heating schedules (Graph 7).

What respondents valued most were the possibility to increase the use of local renewable energy, and cost optimization. The main concerns included installation of too many devices, data privacy and security, as well as losing control over home devices.

Graph 7: Willingness to adopt the service, Switzerland

The less enthusiastic answers from Motta Massagno district compared to other pilot sites are at least partially related to the perceived low level of knowledge of people in energy issues in general and energy communities and energy flexibility in particular. Many were questioning the need to have energy flexibility and expressed concerns over the impact of the ACCEPT solutions on comfort, such as availability of hot water. In this respect, attention should be paid to explaining the purpose of the suggested activities and services, as well as addressing people's questions and concerns related to the activities and services proposed. Some respondents indicate that they have already optimized their energy consumption to the extent possible and did not see how the project would help them to have further savings.

From service creation and user testing perspective, the services should be non-intrusive, guaranteeing the comfort of the customers and carefully considering data privacy and security issues. It could be highlighted how ACCEPT solutions, including the energy community approach, can benefit individual households through benefiting the community as a whole, such as is the case of potential energy savings through a community wide energy use profiling.

5. Tools and services to be tested

ACCEPT project seeks to provide energy communities with digital and governance tools to offer flexibility services to third parties for economic benefits, as well as for intra community energy exchange. ACCEPT will include devices at building level (e.g. devices at households) and at district-level (e.g. district-heating facilities and public EV charging hubs). Using intelligent tools, the project seeks to explore and test different roles that an energy community can potentially play within the energy system and market.

The ACCEPT tools include building management tools, district-level tools, and community-level tools. Most of them will be tested at all pilot sites. Control of district-level assets will be tested at the Dutch and Swiss pilot sites only.

At the pre-validation phase ACCEPT tools will be first tested mainly for operational functionality in the two testbed sites, or laboratories, before full deployment of the solutions into the pilot sites.

The end-user validation process will include three moments or co-creation rounds to test different aspects of the solutions under development:

1st co-creation round: user experience of citizen apps/ interfaces, community management interfaces

2nd co-creation round: assess lived experiences with the full solution

3rd co-creation round: assess lived experiences with the full solution

Participants will receive a full training to the use of ACCEPT tools in the moment of installation. Information channels and feedback mechanism will be established to guarantee information flows from the end-users to technical development and vice-versa to maximise the impact of user testing and end user engagement.

6. Key stakeholders

Establishment of an energy community and engaging members to participate into flexibility markets requires a good understanding of local context, its main characteristics, and the main stakeholders that will be important to the successful introduction of new technologies and services. Community characterization and stakeholder identification were conducted at the first half of the project, and they are reflected in D3.7 submitted in M10. Presentations of ACCEPT project at the pilot sites and recruitment activities conducted during the second half were important steps to build foundations for the successful testing and implementation of ACCEPT solutions throughout the lifetime of the project (D3.5).

In general, the main ACCEPT end-users include consumers, prosumers, building occupants and/ or facility managers for consumer apps and building level solutions, and prosumers and energy community managers or possibly aggregators for community level tools. Residential customers are a key to providing energy flexibility, and hence, attention will be paid to understanding their needs and motivations to join energy demand response and flexibility schemes. Additional relevant stakeholders for the success of ACCEPT solutions, such as energy retailers, Distribution System Operators (DSOs), Balance Responsible Parties (BRPs) or Transmission System Operators (TSOs) might be approached at specific moments as the tools development progresses.

In the following subchapters, stakeholders identified previously in the pilot sites are revisited from the user validation perspective, highlighting relevant stakeholders and user validation activities to be engaged to.

6.1. Aspra Spitia Community, Greece

The main stakeholders in Aspra Spitia community are presented in the Table 4, first elaborated for D3.7. and updated for the user validation process. The relevant stakeholders for user validation are highlighted in green, and stakeholders to be consulted in yellow.

The focus of tools and services to be tested will be residential users in apartments and semi-detached buildings. The residents recruited are expected to be participating to the validation of ACCEPT user interfaces, tools training,

co-creation activities throughout the lifetime of the project. Part of the residents have been approached through facility managers, who might be involved in co-creation or other validation activities at specific moments.

Once ACCEPT services have been tested and further developed, it will be relevant to discuss and validate the services with a local DSO as well.

Table 4: Stakeholders, Aspra Spitia community

Stakeholder	When to interact	Type of interaction(s)
Facility manager	Early (e.g. M10-M14)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Welcome workshop/ACCEPT intro • Tools training • Co-creation activities • Project updates/results share back
Municipality	Early contact (e.g. M10-M14), possibly ongoing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Welcome workshop/ACCEPT intro • Project updates/results share back • Knowledge share on ACCEPT & stadium • ACCEPT 'show and tell' to share results and develop an interest in ACCEPT solutions
Citizens	Ongoing (e.g. M10-M42)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Welcome and bi-yearly workshops • Persona validation workshop • Tools training • Co-creation activities • Project updates/results share back
DSO	Late (e.g. M37-M42)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Workshop to gather feedback about future services
Other industries	Late (e.g. M37-M42)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ACCEPT 'show and tell' to share results and develop an interest in ACCEPT solutions

6.2. Renewable energy cooperative buildings, Spain

The main stakeholders in Murcia, Spain, are presented in the Table 5, first elaborated for D3.7. and updated for the user validation process. The relevant stakeholders for user validation are highlighted in green, and stakeholders to be consulted in yellow.

53 participants that are mainly residential consumers already part of the La Solar energy cooperative will be the main target group for user validation. 16-17 of the participants are prosumers. These stakeholders would participate in user persona workshops, tools training, user interface testing, and co-creation workshops to validate the full ACCEPT tools and services. Citizens in general could be involved in some of the activities especially at a later phase to generate wider interest in the tools and services to be developed.

Table 5: Stakeholders, Murcia, Spain

Stakeholder	When to interact	Type of interaction
Consumer/ prosumer	Ongoing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Welcome workshop/ACCEPT intro • Tools training • User persona validation workshops • Co-creation activities • Project updates/results share back
Municipality	Early (M10-M14), ongoing + maintain	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Welcome workshop/ACCEPT intro • Project updates/results share back
Citizens	Ongoing (e.g. M10-M42)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Welcome workshop/ACCEPT intro • Prosumer/cooperative outreach • Co-creation activities • Project updates/results share back
DSO (AEM, Switzerland)	Mid (M15-30)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Consultation with AEM to exchange experiences on DSO engagement
DSO	Late (e.g. M37-M42)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ACCEPT 'show and tell' to share results and develop an interest in ACCEPT solutions
Other industries	Late (e.g. M37-M42)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ACCEPT 'show and tell' to share results and develop an interest in ACCEPT solutions
Aggregator/ ESCO/ Retailer	Ongoing (ESCOs), late (e.g. M37-M42) (retailers, aggregators)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ACCEPT 'show and tell' to share results and develop an interest in ACCEPT solutions
Business Managers	Late (e.g. M37-M42)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ACCEPT 'show and tell' to share results and develop an interest in ACCEPT solutions

6.3. Eva Lanxmeer Community, the Netherlands

The main stakeholders in Murcia, Spain, are presented in the Table 6, first elaborated for D3.7. and updated for the user validation process. The relevant stakeholders for user validation are highlighted in green, and stakeholders to be consulted in yellow.

Residents of the community participating to the project will be the main stakeholder group for user validation process. The recruitment process is ongoing, and a great share of end-users will be most likely prosumers. The ideal situation would be to engage residents to co-creation activities, however, there is a fear that the potential users are occupied with other ongoing projects in the community. Therefore, the timing and extent of co-creation and user validation sessions will be strategically planned with the pilot leaders resulting in a minimum intrusion to other activities.

Table 6: Stakeholders, Eva Lanxmeer Community, the Netherlands

Stakeholder	When to interact	Type of interaction
Flex market supplier (Energie Samen)	Early (M12-M14)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Co-creation activities
Local energy cooperative	Early (M12-M14), ongoing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Welcome workshop/ACCEPT intro Help with recruiting households Project updates/results share back
Local heating cooperative	Early (M12-M14)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Welcome workshop/ACCEPT intro Help with recruiting households Project updates/results share back
Regional energy company	Early (M12-M14), ongoing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Direct engagement to introduce the project and discuss possibilities around UCs/ BCs for price flexibility
Grid operator	Mid, late (M37-M42)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Direct engagement to present the project and possibly discuss any legal concerns Project updates/results share back
Residents	From Early (M12) and throughout the project	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Welcome workshop/ACCEPT intro Tools training Co-creation activities Project updates/results share back
EV coop platform	Early (M12-M14), possibly ongoing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Direct engagement to introduce the project and discuss demand response testing within the charging points Project updates/results share back
Other businesses	Late (e.g. M37-M42)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ACCEPT 'show and tell' to share results and develop an interest in ACCEPT solutions

6.4. Motta Massagno district, Switzerland

The main stakeholders in Motta Massagno district, Switzerland, are presented in the Table 7, first elaborated for D3.7. and updated for the user validation process. The relevant stakeholders for user validation are highlighted in green, and stakeholders to be consulted in yellow.

The Swiss pilot has two concrete energy communities, one with residential houses, public pool and a football field, and the second one consisting of an elderly care home. Residents and tenants are key participants in the project, as user of ACCEPT tools and through providing energy flexibility. They are key participants to tools training, persona validation workshops, user interface testing and co-creation workshops to test full ACCEPT solutions. Another relevant group for user validation are building owners and managers, especially when they will be directly linked to working with the ACCEPT tools and solutions.

Table 7: Stakeholders, Motta Massagno district, Switzerland

Stakeholder	When to interact	Type of interaction
Building owners/ managers	Early (M12-M14)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Welcome workshop/ACCEPT intro • Engage individually with each of the building owners • Project updates/results share back
Municipality	Throughout the project (M12-M42)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Welcome workshop/ACCEPT intro • Constant communication (i.e. Coordinating the use of workshop spaces etc.) • Project updates/results share back
Pilot site tenants/ citizens/ homeowners	Throughout the project (M12-M42)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Welcome workshop/ACCEPT intro • Tools training • Co-creation activities • Project updates/results share back
Citizens in general	Throughout the project (M12-M42)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Project updates/results share back
Other industries (e.g. TSO, ESCOs)	Mid to final of the project	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Workshops • Project results info/share back

7. Engagement channels for co-creation

ACCEPT co-creation activities include three rounds of sessions with end-users at different moments to validate a range of aspects of ACCEPT solutions including user interfaces and lived experience with the solutions at pilot sites. The methods and possible tools for co-creation activities were first defined and summarized in D3.1, of which an updated version is provided as below:

Table 8: Co-creation methods and tools

Scope	Goal	Methods	Tools
Co-creation	Engage pilot-participants activities designed to 1) explore the community's needs and concerns related to the topic of energy communities and 2) collect feedback on the ACCEPT solutions themselves (e.g. usability, functionalities)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Interviews • Focus groups • Workshops • Questionnaires • User testing • User experience questionnaire (UEQ) • System usability scale (SUS) • Performance analytics 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Maptionnaire (map-based survey software) • Alchemer (survey software) • Balsamiq (wireframing software) • Microsoft Teams • Miro (brainstorming and visual collaboration tool)

As part of the demonstration and co-creation activities, commercial and residential end-customers will be engaged to gather feedback, test and implement the ACCEPT solutions. The aim is to directly engage at least 770 citizens as participants across the four pilot countries during the project lifetime.

Citizen recruitment functioned as a first step towards not only tools and services deployment but also user engagement and subsequent co-creation processes. Citizen recruitment was done primarily through two rounds of ex-ante surveys conducted as part of task T6.1 in WP6. The purpose of the first round of surveys was to gather enough information about the devices available at the different households/buildings, as well as the buildings themselves, to be able to assess their suitability for participating in the project. The second round requires more detailed information on the available devices at the eligible buildings or apartments.

Interactions with citizens have already begun, and good progress has been made with regard to further recruitment across all four pilot sites. Assessment of the suitability of the selected households and end-users is ongoing in all the pilot sites and is expected to be completed between M12-M14. Visits to end-users have been used to clarify doubts and questions related to Accept tools and services.

The first half of the coming year, M13-M18, will include testing of ACCEPT solutions at the testbeds. The engagement activities further continue with co-creation of user personas (see chapter 3) and persona validation workshops at the pilot sites. The development of user personas will help to ensure that the tools and services to be designed will respond to the needs and preferences of different users. This period involves user testing of ACCEPT citizen apps and energy community management interfaces with selected end-users across different pilot sites. Presential workshops will be preferred when existing COVID-19 protocols allow. A range of virtual tools for user testing and engagement are at disposal should we need to rely on virtual engagement strategies.

After a pre-validation at the ACCEPT solutions in the ACCEPT test-bed laboratories from M14-M17 onwards, the solutions will be deployed to the identified participants, who will be trained in the use of the solutions. In addition, ACCEPT user manuals for the software tools will be drafted and released. By the M24, ACCEPT solutions will be fully deployed and operational at the pilot sites.

Co-creation workshops will be organised with ACCEPT participants, including consumers and prosumers at pilot sites, from M26 onwards to receive user feedback on the design and usability of the services including drives that influence the types of digital services the users find most valuable. Barriers to participate and use the services will also be explored, and information to follow KPIs related to user acceptance will be gathered. The first round of testing and co-creation of the ACCEPT solutions as a part of T7.1 will be done during M26-M28, followed by internal feedback round as well as communication the results for the participants and wider ACCEPT community.

The engagement activities will also include further co-creation and solution testing in M35-36 with associated feedback sessions with internal and external audience. From M37 onwards activities related to business model validation will be conducted in the pilot sites, followed by sharing of ACCEPT results to a wider audience.

Apart from the jointly defined engagement actions, each pilot site will continue with individual engagement actions directed to the ACCEPT participants and wider audience. These may include newsletters, information sessions, individualised guidance, social media presence, just to name a few. In the following sub-chapters, engagement activities realised so far within the pilot sites are being shortly summarised. More detailed information on engagement activities is available in D3.2.

7.1. Aspra Spitia Community, Greece

In the Greek pilot, the original recruitment goal was a public football stadium and 63 local residences. The focus has been narrowed to residential customers. A workshop designed to raise awareness of the ACCEPT project and build trust with potential end-users took place in M7. Currently, 55 potential users have expressed their interest in participating in the project and their suitability is currently being assessed through level 2 audits.

7.2. Renewable energy cooperative buildings, Spain

In the Spanish pilot, the recruitment goal is to involve 50 citizens in piloting activities, of which 15 will be prosumers. Following the initial recruitment process, 54 residential users and 17 prosumers have been identified and are being reviewed through level 2 survey to select the final participants who will take part in ACCEPT. A video telco and various correspondences were also undertaken with the goal of recruitment, as well as building confidence in the project with citizens, and opening communication channels with the public in general.

7.3. Eva Lanxmeer Community, the Netherlands

In the Dutch pilot, the aim is to recruit 50 households and 1 business company. Thus far, awareness has been raised in the community through various communication materials. 40 households with assets of interest to the project have been identified and communication with these end-users has been initiated. As a setback not all originally selected households fulfilled all criteria to be selected; the recruitment will continue once technical criteria and requirements have been clarified.

7.4. Motta Massagno district, Switzerland

The Swiss pilot consists of two separate areas, the Arena Innovation Community (AIC) which consist of a residential area in the suburbs of Lugano and Fondazione La Sosta (FLS), an elderly care home within the urban area. The recruitment objectives were to engage with all the residential users (approximately 50 users, one per house), the 4 building owners and the 2 utility managers in the AIC. For the FLS, all 30 users and the management of the elderly care home are targeted. Engagement activities thus far have included information letters, two workshops, one-to-one communication with 63 members of the community, including question and answer sessions and home visits. With regards to the recruitment progress, 50 have signed the agreement with the energy community and it is expected that all citizens will have been engaged by M12.

Overall, the citizens seem to prefer personalized contacts, presential workshops and information communicated in local language.

8. ACCEPT co-creation roadmap

The ACCEPT co-creation roadmap includes 4 co-creation sessions or trainings in each pilot site, and a persona validation workshop session, which will be all implemented according to the timeline provided below. The contents of the workshops have been discussed in the chapter 7.

Key stakeholders for co-creation are ACCEPT participants whose opinions on the function of tools and services are vital for creating tools that meet the needs and preferences of end users. The participants will mainly be consumers and prosumers, but on occasion others, such as building or facility managers. In addition, specific actors, such as business owners or DSOs / BRPs and possibly TSOs could be engaged at specific moments.

The ACCEPT engagement timeline establishes the estimated timing for co-creation workshops and trainings, and how they are related to wider engagement activities:

Table 9: ACCEPT engagement timeline, including user testing and validation activities (in blue)

Timeline	Stakeholders	Description	Activity	Related tasks
Stage 1: User requirements exploration				
M6	External & internal	Collection of market actor and prosumer requirements	Concept test survey	T2.1
M6-14	External & internal	Pilot welcome workshops/ACCEPT introduction event	Workshops	T3.1, T7.1, T3.4
M10	Internal	Feedback per pilot site on Business Cases-Use Cases-System Architecture and Measurement & Verification Methodology	Survey	T2.2, T2.3
M10-12	External	ACCEPT community member concept test results share back	One page newsletter or community presentation	T3.1
M10-42	External	[GREEK pilot] – knowledge share with the municipality on ACCEPT and local football stadium	Consultation	T3.4
M10-42	External	[SPANISH pilot] – Outreach activities aimed at consumers and prosumers	Communication/ dissemination	T3.4
M12-14	Internal & external	[DUTCH pilot] – Recruitment of households through local energy & heating cooperative	Consultations and communication	T3.4 & T6.1
M12-14	Internal & external	[DUTCH pilot] – Direct engagement to introduce the project and discuss possibilities around UCs/ BCs for price flexibility with the regional energy company, and to discuss demand response testing within the charging points with the EV cooperative platform	Consultations	T3.4, T2.1

M12-14	External	[SWISS pilot] – Engage individually with each of the building owners	Consultations and communication	T3.4
M12-42	External	Project results share back with all interested stakeholders	Communication/ dissemination	T3.4, T9.1
M12-15	External & internal	Feedback on Service Level Agreements and contract terms for the business models and services	Survey	T2.5
M12-42	External	[SWISS pilot] – Continued communication with municipality for coordination purposes	Consultations and communication	T3.4
Stage 2: Prototyping validation				
M10-13	External & internal	Participation in ex-ante pilot surveys	Audit	T6.1
M11-12	External	ACCEPT introduction for community members	One page newsletter or community presentation	T3.1, T7.1
M13-14	External	ACCEPT persona validation workshop	4 workshops (one/pilot)*	T3.1, T3.4
M15-16	External & internal	Co-creation workshop 1: Feedback on ACCEPT system 1 st prototype	4 workshops (one/pilot)*	T7.1, T6.2, WP4, WP5
M15-20	Internal	[SPANISH pilot] – consultation with AEM to investigate DSO perspective	Interview	T3.4
M16-M18	External	Community co-creation share back: High level insights from 1 st prototype co-creation workshop	One page newsletter or community presentation	T7.1
M18-M21	Internal	Feedback of pre-validation of ACCEPT tools at test bed sites results	TBD	T6.4
M20-24	External	Scheduling of installation activities and training of pilot participants on the use of ACCEPT solutions	TBD	T6.5, T6.6
M26-27	External & internal	Co-creation workshop 2: Feedback on ACCEPT system 2 nd prototype	4 workshops (one/pilot)*	T7.1, T6.2, WP4, WP5, WP7, WP8
M28-M30	External	Community co-creation share back: High level insights from 2 nd prototype co-creation workshop	One page newsletter or community presentation	T7.1
M35-36	External & internal	Co-creation workshop 3: Feedback on ACCEPT system final prototype	4 workshops (one/pilot)*	T7.1, T6.2, WP7, WP8

M37-M39	External	Community co-creation share back: High level insights from 3 rd prototype co-creation workshop	One page newsletter or community presentation	T7.1
Stage 3: Business modelling validation				
M27-M33	External & internal	Feedback on obstacles for DR application in energy communities	TBD	T8.1
M37-40	External	Feedback on business models	TBD	T8.4
M37-M42	External & internal	Sharing of ACCEPT results with businesses	TBD	T3.4
M37-42	External	[GREEK pilot] – consultation with DSO to discuss future services	Interview	T3.4
M37-42	External	[DUTCH pilot] – direct engagement with Grid operator to present the project and discuss any legal concerns	Interview	T3.4
M37-M42	External	Feedback on exploitable results & business potential	TBD	T8.2

9. Conclusions

Successful implementation of solutions and business models is reliant on gathering stakeholder feedback on products and services from the development stage through to the project’s conclusion. ACCEPT approach to consumer validation includes a three-stage methodology which will be implemented through the Living Lab approach.

ACCEPT services validation methodology is set to guarantee that ACCEPT solutions will meet user preferences and requirements, they will be easy to use, and energy communities will find the solutions useful both for individuals as well as for the community as a whole.

The methodology encompasses three phases: pre-analysis, pre-validation, and user validation as a part of ACCEPT living labs concept. ACCEPT Living Lab coordination activities will guarantee a coherent and coordinated approach to co-creation and user testing, among other things, ensuring a flow of information from technical development to end-users and vice versa.

ACCEPT user validation roadmap includes user persona creation, user testing of consumer and community tools interfaces, and co-validation of consumer’s lived experiences at the pilot sites. At a later stage, also business models will be tested and validated.